

ACRIDINE DERIVATIVES. PART VII. COMPOUNDS WITH MERCURY, COPPER AND ANTIMONY.

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Certain mercury, copper and antimony compounds have been prepared from 5-thiolacridines.

In a previous communication (Das-Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 244) some substituted 5-thiolacridines and their gold and silver salts have been described. In the present paper the gold and silver salts of 5-thiolacridine (I, R=H) have been prepared. In addition to this, certain new salts of mercury, copper and antimony have been prepared from the different 5-thiolacridines.

The sodium salt of 5-thiolacridines when treated with mercuric and mercurous salts give compounds of type (II) and (III) (M=Hg) respectively, (the structure of the compounds III being attributed by analogy). The compounds (II) have been isolated in two different forms, yellow and red.

The two varieties of the above mercuric salt have the same melting point and percentage composition suggesting allotropism. Again the sodium salt of substituted 5-thiolacridine gave with a cupric salt, the compounds (II, M=Cu). The sodium salt of 5-thiolacridine, however, gave with copper sulphate a basic compound.

The antimony compound of the type (I, R=StO) has been prepared by treating the sodium salt of 2-chloro-7-methoxy-5-thiolacridine with potassium antimonyl tartrate. This compound is orange-yellow but when heated at 80°-100° becomes red. The red variety has the same melting point as the former, thus suggesting allotropism.

All these compounds are stable but are usually insoluble in common organic solvents. Amongst this group of compounds the auro as well as the

mercurio compounds seem to be of considerable importance. Their pharmacological properties are being studied.

EXPERIMENTAL.

5-Thiolacridine.—5-Chloroacridine was heated with twice its weight of potassium xanthogenate at 120-30° for 3 hours in phenol solution. The mixture was poured into cold water, the precipitated solids collected, washed with water, and crystallised from rectified spirit in red needles, m.p. 247-49°. (Found: N, 6.51. $C_{13}H_9NS$ requires N, 6.63 per cent).

The compound exists in both ketonic and enolic form. By neutralising a solution of the compound in alcoholic sodium hydroxide, the enolic variety was isolated in yellow needles (m.p. 247-49°) which changed into the red variety (ketonic) in a short time. By determining the p_a of equimolecular solutions of this compound and 2-chloro-7-methoxy-5-thiolacridine in alcohol, it has been found that the former is less acidic. This observation also indicates that the enolic form of 5-thiolacridine is comparatively less stable.

5-Aurothioacridine was prepared just like the aurothioacridines, previously described (*loc. cit.*). The compound was isolated as a red powder, m.p. 288-90°. (Found: Au, 50.0 $C_{13}H_9NSAu$ requires Au, 48.4 per cent).

5-Argentothioacridine.—5-Thiolacridine was dissolved in alcohol and equivalent amount of silver nitrate in aqueous solution was added when a red precipitate was obtained. This was filtered, washed with alcohol and water and dried to a red powder, m.p. 278-80°. (Found: Ag, 34.1. $C_{13}H_9NSAg$ requires Ag, 33.96 per cent).

Mercurio-di-5-thio-(2-chloro-7-methoxy)acridine.—2-Chloro-7-methoxy-5-thiolacridine (0.11 g.) was dissolved in about 10 c.c. of alcohol containing sodium hydroxide (4 c.c. of N/10 solution). To this, a solution of mercuric chloride (0.05 g. in 5 c.c. of water) was slowly added and the mixture shaken and left for sometime, when a yellow precipitate settled down. It was filtered, washed with alcohol and water and dried in a steam-oven to a yellow powder, m.p. 284-85°. The compound is soluble in water-alcohol and other common solvents, yield theoretical. [Found: N, 3.82; Hg, 26.2. $(C_{14}H_9ONClS)_2Hg$ requires N, 3.73; Hg, 26.76 per cent].

In the above preparation, if a lesser amount of sodium hydroxide be used, the compound isolated was sometimes red instead of yellow. The red compound also melted at 284° and, mixed melting point with the yellow compound was not depressed. It gave similar results on analysis. [Found: N, 3.6; Hg, 27.31. $(C_{14}H_9ONClS)_2Hg$ requires N, 3.73; Hg, 26.76

per cent]. Evidently the yellow and the red compounds are allotropic modifications. The yellow compound also becomes red when treated with acids, but it is changed to yellow again on treatment with alkali. This red compound is quite different from the former which is not changed by alkali or heating.

Mercurio-di-5-thio-(7-methoxy)acridine.—7-Methoxy-5-thiolacridine (1 mol.), dissolved in alcohol containing 1 mol. of sodium hydroxide, was mixed with an aqueous mercuric chloride ($\frac{1}{2}$ mol.) solution. After similar treatment as in the previous case, the compound was isolated as yellow powder, m.p. 254°, exhibiting similar properties. [Found: N, 4.23; Hg, 30.0. (C₁₄H₁₀NS)₂Hg requires N, 4.11; Hg, 29.47 per cent].

Mercurio-di-5-thioacridine.—It was prepared from 5-thiolacridine and mercuric chloride in the usual way as a yellow powder, m.p. 298-300° (decomp.). [Found: Hg, 32.53. (C₁₃H₈NS₂)₂Hg requires Hg, 32.32 per cent].

5-Mercurothio-(2-chloro-7-methoxy)acridine.—2-Chloro-7-methoxy-5-thiolacridine (0.11 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (100 c.c.) containing sodium hydroxide (0.016 g.) and mercurous nitrate (0.12 g. finely powdered) was added and the mixture stirred for several hours when a yellow precipitate was obtained. It was collected, washed with alcohol, and dried to a yellow powder, m.p. 307-8°. [Found: N, 3.27; Hg, 40.85. (C₁₄H₈ONClS₂Hg)₂ requires N, 2.95; Hg, 42.22 per cent]. The compound becomes red when treated with dilute acids, but again becomes yellow when heated at about 150°. It is insoluble in common solvents.

5-Mercurothio-(7-methoxy)acridine.—7-Methoxy-5-thiolacridine (1 mol.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol containing sodium hydroxide (1 mol.) and powdered mercurous nitrate (1 mol.) was added. After usual treatment, the compound (yellow) melted at 244-45°. [Found: N, 3.4; Hg, 46.9. (C₁₄H₁₀ONS₂Hg)₂ requires N, 3.27; Hg, 45.52 per cent]. It exhibits similar properties.

5-Mercurothioacridine was prepared from 5-thiolacridine and mercurous nitrate in the usual way as a yellow powder, m.p. 293-94° (decomp.). [Found: Hg, 47.52. (C₁₃H₈NS₂Hg)₂ requires Hg, 48.86 per cent].

Cupro-di-5-thio-(2-chloro-7-methoxy)acridine.—2-Chloro-7-methoxy-5-thiolacridine (2 mol.) was dissolved in alcohol containing sodium hydroxide (2 mol.). Aqueous solution (1%) of copper sulphate (1 mol.) was slowly added, and the mixture shaken for some time and left for several hours, when a pinkish brown precipitate was obtained. It was collected, washed with alcohol and water and dried in a steam-oven to a brownish powder, m.p. 291-93° (decomp.). [Found: N, 3.81; Cu, 9.20.

$(C_{14}H_9ONClS)_2Cu, 4H_2O$ requires N, 4.09; Cu, 9.28 per cent]. The compound contains four molecules of water of crystallisation, which are not removed on heating at 120° but a portion is lost when heated at 150° . The compound is insoluble in water but very sparingly soluble in alcohol, yield theoretical.

Cupro-di-5-thio-(7-methoxy)acridine was prepared from 7-methoxy-5-thiolacridine and copper sulphate solution in the usual way as brownish powder and has been found to possess similar properties, m.p. $313-14^\circ$ (decomp.). [Found: Cu, 10.23. $(C_{14}H_{10}ONS)_2Cu, 4H_2O$ requires Cu, 10.33 per cent].

Cupro-di-5-thiolacridine (basic).—5-Thiolacridine was dissolved in alcohol containing equivalent amount of caustic soda and treated with copper sulphate solution in the usual way. An almost black compound was isolated, m.p. $284-88^\circ$ (decomp.). The compound seems to be of basic nature. [Found: Cu, 22.0. $(C_{14}H_9NS)_2Cu, CuO$ requires Cu, 22.5 per cent].

Antimonyl-5-thio-(2-chloro-7-methoxy)acridine.—2-Chloro-7-methoxy-5-thiolacridine (1 mol.) was dissolved in alcohol (90%) containing sodium hydroxide (1 mol.). An aqueous solution of sodium antimonyl tartrate (1 mol.) was added and the mixture shaken and left for some time, when an orange-yellow precipitate settled, which was filtered, washed with alcohol and water and dried in vacuum to an orange-yellow powder, m.p. 256° . (Found: N, 3.45; Sb, 29.07. $C_{14}H_9O_2NCISSb$ requires N, 3.4; Sb, 29.52 per cent). It becomes deep red when heated in a steam-oven. Melting point of a mixture of the yellow and the red varieties was not depressed. The red variety gave similar results on analysis. (Found: N, 3.39; Sb, 29.2. $C_{14}H_9O_2NCISSb$ requires N, 3.4; Sb, 29.52 per cent).

The yellow and the red varieties are evidently the allotropic modifications of the same compound.

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